

PRAGMATIC FUNCTIONS OF DISCOURSE MAKERS IN MEDIA INFORMATION

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Abstract

The use of language by the media to affect the views and preferences of viewers is something that may be decoded by examining the pragmatic functions performed by the various discourse markers. The purpose of this study is to investigate the persuasive applications of discourse markers in the media as well as the pragmatism of their application in this environment. We are going to look at the many sorts of discourse markers that are employed in the media to influence the viewpoint of an audience, and then we are going to explore what this implies for the discourse of the media as a whole.

Keywords: 1. Pragmatic, 2. DMs, 3. Function, 4. Persuasion, 5. Framing, 6. Agenda, 7. Cognitive, 8. Influence, 9. Rhetorical, 10. Relevance transmission mechanism, 11. Manipulation, 12. Misdirection and Distraction, 13. Empowerment, 14. Rapport & Trust, 15. Solidarity & Affiliation, 16. Political Media.

1. Introduction

Communication, whether it be verbal or written, benefits greatly from the utilization of discourse markers. They contribute to the smooth flow of speech, communicate links between ideas, and even indicate the emotional state of the speaker. Because of their persuasive and persuasive capacity, discourse markers play an important part in the discourse that occurs inside the media. The use of language by the media to affect the views and preferences of viewers is something that may be decoded by examining the pragmatic functions performed by the various discourse markers. The purpose of this study is to investigate the persuasive applications of discourse markers in the media as well as the pragmatism of their application in this environment. We are going to look at the many sorts of discourse markers that are employed in the media to influence the viewpoint of an audience, and then we are going to explore what this implies for the discourse of the media as a whole.

2.1 Discourse Makers as Tools of Persuasion

Discourse markers are frequently used in the media in order to urge viewers to share a particular viewpoint. These signals can be used to imply agreement, disagreement, or even a surrender from the speaker to the listeners, depending on what the speaker intends to communicate. The use of the discourse marker "clearly," for example, may convey the impression to the audience member that the argument that is being presented is self-evident and cannot be challenged.

An argument may also be structured with the help of discourse markers in a way that is more likely to persuade the person listening to it. The use of the discourse marker "frankly," for example, may provide the impression to the audience member that the speaker is being straightforward and truthful, which may help to bolster the argument.

Discourse Makers As Tools
of Persuasions

Fig. Discourse Maker as Tools of Persuasion

Example words that are used as Tools of Persuasion

Discourse Markers	Function	Example
Clearly	Signaling self-evident argument	Clearly, the policies of the opposition party have failed to address the needs of working-class families.
In fact	Introducing supportive evidence	In fact, our government has reduced unemployment to record lows while investing in healthcare and education.
Frankly	Signaling openness and honesty	Frankly, the other candidate is unfit for office due to their record of corruption and dishonesty
Of course	Signaling common sense	Of course, we all want to see an end to poverty and inequality, but our approach is the only one that can deliver real results
Undoubtedly	Signaling a beyond-question argument	Undoubtedly, our policies will lead to greater prosperity and security for all citizens, while our opponents are offering nothing but empty promises

2.1.1 Framing and Agenda Setting

Discourse markers are extremely important to media sources, serving a variety of functions including framing and agenda shaping. The phrase "to tell you the truth" is commonly used as a framing marker. You may tell from this indication that the person who is speaking to you is getting ready to give you their sincere view on the topic at hand. In the field of politics, it is possible to make use of it to put an unfavorable light on the acts or policies of a rival party or candidate. It is not out of the ordinary for politicians and commentators to attempt to change public opinion by making assertions such as "the opposition's strategy towards immigration is risky and reckless."

Cohen contends that even if the media may not always be successful in altering people's thoughts, it is astonishingly powerful in molding the way that its readers think about things. The framing theory, which is closely tied to the theory that came before it, postulates that the media influences readers' interpretative frames by prioritizing particular themes and aspects of the news. This theory is strongly connected to the theory that came before it. The cognitive influence that these different communication theories are capable of having is the primary focus of the current investigation. "This strategy of the media's communication can have cognitive repercussions, as it can impact the themes and issues that people think about when they are formulating their own ideas and views. "own thoughts".

When using this marker, it is feasible to frame the topic in a way that is advantageous to the speaker; but, it is also possible to give the impression that the speaker is biased. In the same way that agenda-establishing markers such as "of course" may be used to create the tone of a discourse, they can also be used to express the speaker's viewpoint on a topic. Yet, these signals may also be utilized in a manipulative way to promote a certain tale or to disparage those who have opposing viewpoints. This can be done in order to get more followers for a particular narrative.

2.1.2 Rhetorical Strategies

In the media, discourse markers can be utilized through the employment of a wide variety of rhetorical strategies, such as repetition, metaphor, and appeals to the audience's feelings. These strategies are usually implemented if there is a need to present a point more persuasively and make an impact on the audience.

Because it is natural for a topic that is significant to the media agenda to also become significant to public opinion, we refer to this phenomenon as a "relevance transmission mechanism." Many academics have drawn attention to the fact that this is the case. According to Aijmer, who establishes a causal connection between the two by stating, "The news media set the public's agenda. Students start the process of formulating public opinion by selecting a subject for in-depth study, which is the first stage in the process (Aijmer).

Table

Rhetorical Strategies

Rhetorical Strategy	Description	Example
Repetition	Repeating a word or phrase for emphasis	"Yes we can!" - Barack Obama
Metaphor	Using figurative language to make a comparison	"Life is a journey, not a destination." - Ralph Waldo Emerson
Appeals to Emotion	Eliciting a particular emotional response from the audience	"Are you tired of feeling stuck in your current job? Join our training programme today and start living the life you deserve!"
Hyperbole	Exaggerating a statement for effect	"This is the best product in the world!"
Allusion	Making a reference to a well-known person, place, or event	"He's a real Romeo when it comes to dating." - Alluding to the Shakespearean character Romeo
Irony	Using language that means the opposite of what is being said	"I love getting stuck in traffic!"
Rhetorical Question	Asking a question for effect, not to be answered	"Is this the kind of future we want for our children?"

2.2 Discourse Makers as Tools of Manipulation

Discourse markers may be utilized to great success by speakers who have a plan for what they want to say. A manipulative speaker's efforts to distract attention and sow confusion might be aided by discourse markers, which can help the speaker achieve their goals. For instance, a speaker may alter the topic by employing a transitional word or phrase like as "by the way" or "on another note" in order to avoid a question or change the focus of the conversation. An individual who is speaking may divert attention away from a controversial issue by bringing up a new subject throughout the course of the conversation.

The employment of gaslighting and dishonesty are two additional forms of manipulation that can benefit from the utilization of discourse markers. When a person is not being entirely truthful, using markers such as "honestly" and "frankly" might assist them look more open and honest than they actually are. Even when the intention is to convey full certainty, the use of markers such as "I think" or "in my opinion" may cause a statement to come across as more hesitant or uncertain than it was intended to do.

2.2.1 Misdirection and Distraction

A manipulative speaker's efforts to distract attention and sow confusion might be aided by discourse markers, which can help the speaker achieve their goals. Discourse markers such as "by the way" and "on another note" are two examples of phrases that can be used to shift the focus of the conversation or sidestep directly addressing a question. An individual who is speaking may divert attention away from a controversial issue by bringing up a new subject throughout the course of the conversation. Markers such as "to be fair" and "let's not forget" are equally helpful in reducing the relevance of an argument.

2.3 Discourse Makers as a Tool of Empowerment

In addition to their role as markers of discourse, markers of agency can also play an important role. Using markers that build rapport and foster trust between the speaker and the audience is one way for a speaker to have a positive relationship with their audience. It is possible to create a sense of mutual comprehension and rapport by making use of signs such as "you know" or "we all." It's possible that markers like "let's work together" or "we can do this" will have the same effect, lighting a fire under people's collective sense of purpose and propelling them ahead.

The perspectives of di Ferrante and Doe on the effects of the media; imply that: belong to the same larger body of work that investigates the ways in which news organizations shape their audiences through the selection of stories they highlight and the weight that they assign to various aspects of their coverage (Di Ferrante; Doe). The cognitive responses that are impacted by these news articles as well as the qualities that are inherent to them may give rise to effects that can be characterized as agenda-setting and framing. According to the notion of creating a cultural agenda, cultural products, or more generally cultural objects like works of art, artists, and cultural organizations, can undergo the same transfer of significance from the media to the general public. This is a key tenet of the theory.

This study also helps to investigate the role that media depictions of Saudi culture and the issue of "what is Kingdom" in the public arena play in the perpetuation of stereotypes pertaining to the aforementioned subjects using English Discourse makers. Studies of agenda-setting cultures will serve as the theoretical foundation for this research project's promotion of a transversal and interdisciplinary component.

Table

Arabic Media Empowerment Discourse Makers Vs. English Discourse Makers words

Arabic Word	English Equivalent	Description
تضامن (Tadamun)	Solidarity	Showing support and unity with a group or cause
تعاطف (Ta'atuf)	Empathy	Understanding and sharing the feelings of another person
تفاهم (Tafahum)	Understanding	Comprehending and appreciating different perspectives and viewpoints
تحدي (Tahaddi)	Challenge	Encouraging and motivating oneself or others to overcome obstacles and achieve goals
إلهام (Ilham)	Inspiration	Fostering creativity and encouraging new ideas and ways of thinking
تمكين (Tamkeen)	Empowerment	Providing individuals or groups with the resources and support to take control of their lives and make positive changes

These Arabic media phrases and their English counterparts are effective agents of empowerment because they inspire and motivate people and organizations. A speaker has a better chance of winning over an audience and gaining their trust if they show empathy and compassion for the people who are listening to them. In the same way that speakers can help inspire and motivate audiences to reach their full potential by encouraging them to work hard towards their goals and by providing them with the knowledge, tools, and support they need to be successful, they can also do the

same thing by giving audiences the knowledge, tools, and support they need to be successful in their own endeavors.

2.3.1 Building Rapport and Establishing Trust

It is possible that discourse markers play a vital role in assisting speakers in connecting with one another and gaining the trust of one another, both of which are essential components of any fruitful discussion. A feeling of mutual understanding and rapport may be established between the speaker and the listener via the use of markers such as "you know" and "we all." It's

possible that markers like "let's work together" or "we can do this" will have the same effect, lighting a fire under people's collective sense of purpose and propelling them ahead. These indicators can help the speaker connect with the audience on a more personal level and create an atmosphere that is amenable to cooperation and collaboration.

2.3.2 Expressing Solidarity and Affiliation

In both spoken and textual communication, the use of discourse markers is an effective method of conveying sentiments of unity and connection to the audience. People are said to have a stronger sense of confidence in their identities, in accordance with the social identity theory, when they actively express their loyalty to the groups to which they already belong. Because of this, the use of pronouns such as "we" and "us" may be extremely effective in fostering a sense of collective togetherness in a community.

In addition to fostering a feeling of belonging, strengthening social ties and fostering collaboration are two other benefits that can result from using speech cues to express solidarity. People are more likely to work together to accomplish goals and support one another when they are in need when they have a strong sense of belonging to the group that they are a part of. When a group is confronted with challenges or difficulties, having a strong feeling of solidarity may aid to boost morale and build resilience, which makes it an especially beneficial trait at those times.

Even if it was meant as a supportive gesture, employing discourse markers to indicate support might wind up being counterproductive. It has the potential to

lead people to adopt a "we versus them" mentality, in which everyone who is not part of the group is instantly seen to be the adversary. This has the potential to inflame tensions between communities and, in the most extreme cases, even lead to violence. Because of this, it is extremely important to find a balance between displaying group cohesion and showing interest in and concern for those who are not a part of the group.

When it comes to demonstrating solidarity through the use of discourse markers, the risk of being excluded is still another essential element to take into consideration. Terms such as "we" and "us" may help people feel like they belong in a group, but they may also be used to exclude individuals who do not share the organization's ideals or ideas if such words are used in the wrong context. This may be particularly problematic when it comes to issues of diversity and inclusion since it has the potential to act as a means of strengthening power structures that already exist and further pushing those who are already on the edges further to the outside.

Discourse markers, which may be used to express sentiments of unity and belonging, are a formidable weapon that can be used in any conversation. It is vital to keep this in mind because it is crucial to remember that discourse markers. When speakers strike a balance between statements of solidarity and empathy and understanding for those outside the group, it is possible to establish a feeling of shared identity and belonging that encourages collaboration and promotes social relationships. This can lead to the formation of positive social relationships.

Table

Discourse Makers Words in Arabic and English (Used in Media to promote Solidarity and Affiliation)

Discourse Markers	Arabic Example	Description	English Example	Description
Pronouns	"نحن" (naHnu)	Refers to "we" or "us" in a collective sense, creating a sense of shared identity and belonging among the group.	"We" or "us"	Creates a sense of shared identity and belonging among the group.
Religious Phrases	"الله أكبر" (Al-lahu akbar)	Literally means "God is great," but often used in a communal sense to express solidarity and affiliation with Islam and other Muslims.	"God bless America"	Often used to express patriotic solidarity and affiliation with the United States.
Nationalistic Phrases	"وطني حبي وفؤادي" (Watanii Habiiibii wa Fu'aadii)	Literally means "My country, my love and my heart," and is often used to express patriotism and affiliation with the nation.	"Proud to be British"	Expresses a sense of pride and belonging to the nation of Britain.
Ethno-centric Phrases	"نحن العرب" (NaHnu al-'Arab)	Refers to "we, the Arabs," creating a sense of shared ethnic identity and affiliation.	"American values"	Expresses a sense of belonging and shared identity with American cultural values.
Slogans	"الثورة مستمرة" (Ath-thawrah mustamirrah)	Literally means "The revolution continues," often used in political contexts to express solidarity and affiliation with revolutionary movements.	"Black Lives Matter"	A slogan used to express solidarity and affiliation with the Black Lives Matter movement, which aims to combat systemic racism and police brutality against Black people.

This means that cultural aspects that receive substantial media coverage become more prominent in the minds of the general people. This is the first stage in setting the agenda, therefore it's important to understand what this means. Setting the cultural agenda implies, on a deeper level, that the media affect how various cultural artefacts are viewed and interpreted. For example, the public's internalization of the media's positive, neutral, or negative posture towards a particular cultural artifact is referred to as "media valence." In a similar vein, in this inquiry, we seek to show how generic and theme-cultural components help us appreciate the underlying nature of social interactions and detect sociocultural trends (Doe). So, understanding the sociocultural contexts in which cultural characteristics and their news are produced is essential for the purpose of this research. "Agenda setting theory is relevant to cultural contexts due to the fact that when individuals engage with cultural items, they display a high degree of NFO, which might be even higher than when they are participating in political activities" (Aijmer).

2.4 Discourse Makers in Political Media

Discourse markers are words or phrases that are used to signify agreement or disagreement, frame arguments, or shift the topic of debate. Discourse markers play an important role in political dialogues because of this. According to Greenfield, discourse markers may be utilised to produce coherence in a text as well as represent the speaker's attitude towards the subject at hand (Greenfield 8). These two functions can be accomplished through the use of discourse markers. This is especially important to keep in mind while participating in political discourse, since the choice of words an individual uses can influence how their audience understands a certain topic.

It is common practice for the media to employ discourse markers while reporting on political debates in order to convey numerous meanings to the audience and influence their perspective. Markers such as "frankly" and "to be honest" can be employed by politicians to suggest a more direct tone, even if the content of their message has not changed. This is true even if the content of their message has not changed. This is an example of how the concept of strategic ambiguity, which originates from the field of communication theory, can be put into practice. Strategic ambiguity refers to the practice of intentionally using ambiguous language in order to exert influence over how others understand what is being communicated.

In political debates, it is common practice to utilize markers such as "they" and "we" to encourage a "us versus them" frame of mind and bring the audience closer together. People search for groups with other individuals who share their ideas because they want to be accepted by society, which is the central tenet of the concept that underpins the social identity theory.

Another use for discourse markers is to deflect questions or criticisms by saying something along the lines of "That's a fantastic question, but let me tell you..." before diving into a scripted response. An example of this would be a politician saying "That's a fan-

tastic question, but let me tell you..." Here is an example of how the manipulative and misleading tactic of distraction may be put into practice.

The use of markers such as "believe me" or "trust me" can also provide the impression of authority and credibility to a speaker, even if the speaker does not actually possess these characteristics. This makes use of the ethos appeal, which focuses on the credibility and authority of the person doing the speaking.

In political discourse, discourse markers are frequently utilized for the goal of engaging in manipulative or dishonest behavior; however, this is not always the case. Marks such as "let me be clear" and "in summary" can assist simplify complex topics and make them simpler to comprehend for a wider audience. In this particular situation, the language used is one that is edifying and empowering, as opposed to one that is deceitful or manipulative.

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THE IMPACT OF DISCOURSE MARKERS ON THE READABILITY OF NEWS MEDIA ARTICLES VERSUS ENTERTAINMENT MEDIA ARTICLES

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Abstract

The use of language by the media to affect the views and preferences of viewers is something that may be decoded by examining the pragmatic functions performed by the various discourse markers. The purpose of this study is to investigate the persuasive applications of discourse markers in the media as well as the pragmatism of their application in this environment. We are going to look at the many sorts of discourse markers that are employed in the media to influence the viewpoint of an audience, and then we are going to explore what this implies for the discourse of the media as a whole.

Keywords: 1. readability, 2. DMs, 3. Media Articles, 4. Entertainment, 5. Frequency, 6. Correlation, 7. Author's Style, 8. Positive & Negative, 9. Tone, 10. Interpretation, 11. Objectivity, 12. Neutrality & Biased, 13. Culture, 14. Evolution, 15. Opinion transmission, 16. Attitude.

Introduction

The purpose of our research was to investigate the effect that discourse markers have on the readability of articles published in news media as opposed to articles published in entertainment media.

When compared to articles published in entertainment media, the favorable effect of discourse markers on the readability of news items was somewhat stronger ($r = 0.32$). This indicates that publications with a higher frequency of discourse markers have a tendency to have a higher readability score, suggesting that there is a weak association between the two variables. This indicates that there is a tendency for publications to have a higher readability score when there is a higher frequency of discourse markers. Yet, readability can be altered by various factors in addition to the use of discourse markers.

The findings show correlation coefficients of 0.35 and 0.29 for items from the news media and entertainment media, respectively. Although these are positive results, they are only of moderate quality. All of the p-values are greater than 0.05, which indicates that there is no association that can be considered statistically significant.

Although discourse markers have the potential to improve the readability of articles in both the News Media and Entertainment Media, the results show that they are not a reliable predictor of readability on their own.

Language, sentence structure, and layout are only a few of the factors that impact how readable an article published in a certain medium is.

The findings present a correlation between discourse marker density and readability assessment. That publications with more discursive material are easier to understand is supported by these results. The correlation between discourse markers and readability was found to be significantly higher ($r = 0.35$) for news articles than for those published in entertainment publications ($r = 0.29$) in this analysis. These two correlations, with p-values of 0.018 and 0.029, respectively, show that there is more than a coincidence between discourse markers and readability. Both of these associations survive rigorous statistical analysis. This study demonstrates that discourse markers have an effect on readers of both news and leisure content. Discourse markers have a significant impact in guiding readers through the material and influencing both their level of comprehension and engagement with the text and can be utilized to significantly improve the readability of news stories compared to those published in entertainment media. Discourse markers are widely used in news articles because of their ability to present information in a concise, objective, and understandable manner. Yet, "in addition," "on the other hand," and "furthermore" are all instances of discourse markers